

EFFECT OF TACKIFICATION ON IN-PLANE SHEAR BEHAVIOURS OF BIAXIAL WOVEN FABRICS IN BIAS EXTENSION TEST

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Introduction

In this work, based on the distinctive load fluctuation observed during bias extension tests of CF3031 biaxial woven fabrics with varying tackifier content, we established a new model called "Gradual Deformation Model" as deformation assumption to describe the different bias extension behaviours of tackified woven fabrics. The model validation was implemented sufficiently via digital image correlation technology and finite element analysis. Due to the good correlation between experimental and numerical results, it is reasonable to claim that the main effect of tackification on in-plane shear behaviours is the formation of great resistance to inter-tow shear, inter-tow sliding and cross-over point sliding.

Materials and Tackification process

The 4-harness satin weave fabric CF3031 was used in current work. ET5284 epoxy resin powder was chosen as the tackifier.

The ET5284 tackifier powder was applied uniformly on one side of woven fabric by a 120 mesh sieve. Then, powder sprayed fabric was heated by an IR lamp to fuse tackifier powders to fabric surface.

Photographs of woven fabric CF3031: (a) untackified, (b) tackified

Characterization of in-plane shear behaviours

Mechanical behaviours in bias extension test

Obvious distinction can be observed at initial stage of deformation. For untackified specimen, bias extension curve rises smoothly, while for tackified specimens, obvious fluctuation shows up at the very beginning of bias extension curves. The local peak load at the beginning of tests performs a remarkable growth trend with higher loading of tackifier on woven fabrics. The rapid increase for load of bias extension test may be caused by the enhanced resistance of fiber yarns to deformation, resulting from the tackifier adhered to the surface of woven fabric.

DIC (Digital Image Correlation) Investigation

In order to understand the global and local shear behaviour of biaxial woven fabrics in bias extension test comprehensively, DIC was engaged in this work. As depicted in Fig. 3, it is clear that the deformation of untackified specimen follows the PJN assumption exactly. With tackifier applied on woven fabrics, the deformation pattern does not follow PJN assumption any more, in which zone A occupying most of the investigation area.

Schematic of classical deformation mechanism in bias extension test

Load-displacement curves of CF3031 woven fabrics with and without tackifier in bias extension tests

DIC (GOM® ARAMIS)

Major strain contours of CF3031 woven fabrics with different amount of tackifier in bias extension tests with a 10 mm displacement: (a) 0 wt%, (b) 2.5 wt%, (c) 5.0 wt% and (d) 10.0 wt%

Model proposing and FEA verification

Gradual Deformation Model

Based on the results above, we propose a reasonable assumption named Gradual Deformation Model (GDM).

Gradual Deformation Model for shear deformation of tackified woven fabrics in bias extension test

Simulation of tackifier deformation process in the bias extension test of tackified woven fabrics

FEA Verification

Although quantitative differences exist between experiments and numerical model, the load fluctuation phenomenon, unique edge shape and GMD deformation for tackified specimens were reproduced successfully.

Finite element model of tackified CF3031 woven fabrics

Comparison of load-displacement curves in bias extension test between experiment and simulation

Our Group

Our research interests focus on the deformation behaviours of fabric under various conditions and their simulation.

